

1 **Genitourinary infection dynamics modeled in human cells.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Our laboratory utilizes advanced cell culture systems (e.g., iPS stem cell culture and patient derived
8 induced pluripotent stem cells) and next generation sequencing methods (RNA-sequencing) to study the
9 cell and molecular biology underlying cancer, infection and chronic disease in humans. GU infection in the
10 community Here we established and studied a cell culture model of genitourinary infection. Chlamydia
11 trachomatis infection of primary vaginal epithelial cells in culture coupled with RNA-sequencing revealed
12 activation of ribonuclease A family member 7 *RNASE7* by infection of the GU tract. We demonstrate here
13 that infection of cells of the GU tract result in activation of the plasminogen effector PLAUR. C.
14 Trachomatis infection activated *IL-24*, *IFI27*, *NFKBIZ* and *MYD88*. *CXCL16* activation and *RIG-I/DDX60*
15 induction marked Chlamydia infection of the vagina.

16 Citations

- 17
- 18 1. Foxman, B., 2010. The epidemiology of urinary tract infection. Nature Reviews Urology, 7(12),
19 pp.653-660.
 - 20 2. Laupland, K.B., Ross, T., Pitout, J.D.D., Church, D.L. and Gregson, D.B., 2007. Community-onset
21 urinary tract infections: a population-based assessment. Infection, 35(3), p.150.
 - 22 3. Schaeffer, A.J., 2002. Infection and inflammation of the genitourinary tract. The journal of urology,
23 167(4), pp.1926-1935.

24
25
26
27
28
GSE228774